

Munir's Slime Pattern of Domestic Violence

Dr. Munir Moosa Sadruddin

Munir's Slime Pattern is a predictive tool that can help identify potential indicators of domestic violence. The pattern was developed through case-based ethnographic analysis.

Unfortunately, a significant number of individuals subjected to violence choose to remain silent, granting their tormentors the power to continue their hurtful actions. It is important to note that victims are not always wrong in remaining silent, as they may feel compelled to submit their lives to the abuser due to societal pressures, a lack of empowerment, or emotional attachment.

The model recognizes five distinct stages¹ in the progression of domestic violence.

1. **Passiveness-** The culprit manipulates their victim through a facade of affection, showering them with compliments, and sentimental gestures, and fulfilling most of their desire. Their ultimate aim is to build trust through any means necessary. They exhibit excessive possessiveness, appearing dignified and trustworthy, while concealing any potential threats to their victim. They reveal some aspects of their personal life, both past and present, yet seek to know everything about the victim, including their weaknesses, strengths, likes, dislikes, fears, and aspirations. They also assess the willingness and obedience of the victim through tests and trials in a manipulative manner, often causing victims to fall prey to their intentions without fully understanding their true motives.
2. **Isolation-** The culprit begins trapping the victim through psychological tactics. They create a sense of indebtedness for their kindness. They start giving fake promises, feel sorry for everything, and emphasize positive aspects while taking responsibility for their errors, mistakes, and negligence. Their primary objective is to confuse the victim and manipulate their thoughts, causing them to constantly think about the culprit and hindering their decision-making abilities. During this phase, culprits infuse their ideology and alienate loved ones from the victim.
3. **Indirect threats-** The culprit now begins to employ indirect threats, both verbal and physical, as a means of gauging the victim's tolerance and capacity for trauma. They meticulously calculate and observe their actions before making any significant moves. They are keen observers and assess when to isolate the victim, often targeting them when they are alone without alerting others. As a result, victims often remain silent and begin to feel burdened, as by this stage, they have become like puppets.
4. **Progression to ongoing physical assaults-** The culprit has understood that through their manipulation, the victim has been conditioned to keep the abuse to themselves, in most cases. If no action is taken, the victim will face repetitive physical attacks (Phases 2 and 3 are infused).

¹ Perpetrator can switch unpredictably to any phase.

5. Clinical depression, compulsive suicide, or murder- Self-explanatory.

Note: Perpetrators are smart observers, so providing them with even a small hint can broaden the trap net for the victim. The sequence is not always predictable. At times, the perpetrator may linger at one phase, particularly during the initial stages, to deceive others. The victim should be empowered enough to cease providing opportunities for the perpetrator to expand their influence. The only solution is to be open to realities and not conceal anything from well-wishers.